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OIKONET A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The dissemination activities carried out at the local level during the OIKONET project are compiled in this document. The activities are presented according to the following structure:

- **Printed and Web Media.** This includes news and reports of the project activities in blogs and websites of the partner organizations; reports published in local conferences; works published in yearbooks produced by partner schools; leaflets and brochures.

- **Events.** Presentation of the project results in events organized by the partners' organizations. They include presentations of the works done in specific activities such as workshops and collaborative learning spaces, as well as reflections on the work about pedagogical innovation carried out in the project.

- **Radio and television.** Workshops, participatory actions and learning activities have been disseminated through local radio and television programs.

- **Websites.** Information about the project activities disseminated through the websites of partner organizations.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and target group

Project activities have been disseminated through local media, in various ways: in printed and on-line media, presented in events taking place in the partner organizations and broadcasted on television and radio. Some of the dissemination activities have been interwoven with specific activities such as collaborative learning spaces, workshops and participatory actions. These dissemination activities were aimed to local stakeholders directly related with the activities (local authorities, citizens); experts and professionals in the field of housing studies and pedagogical innovation, and academics (faculty members in the partner organizations not directly involved in the OIKONET project).

1.2 Contribution of partners

The contributions of partners to disseminate the project activities at the local level, in different media are summarized next.

- P1 LA SALLE- School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, Spain
 - Announcements of the “Thinking Dwelling” programme
 - Publication of the outcomes of the first edition of “Thinking Dwelling”
 - Interview in Radio Ciutat Vella about the work done in “Housing Systems”
 - Presentation of OIKONET work on pedagogical innovation at the “Jornades d’Innovació Docent”, Barcelona
- P2 ETSA-UPV- School of Architecture of Valencia, Spain
 - Chapters in the book “Selección de Proyectos”.
- P4 KUL- Faculty of Architecture, KU Leuven, Gent/Brussels, Belgium
 - Presentation at the LESEC Annual Event, 2016
- P11 OAPPCR- Ordine degli Architetti, Pianificatori, Paesaggisti e Conservatori della Provincia di Rimini Italy
 - A brochure (in Italian) summarizing the activities of the participatory action in Rimini
 - Conference “Housing sociale e partecipazione di comunità”, Rimini
- P17 PFZ- Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, Croatia
 - Article about the OIKONET project and the first international conference in Barcelona, 2014
 - Article about the OIKONET project and the second international conference in Bratislava, 2015
- P21 SOSTRE CIVIC, Barcelona, Spain
 - TV report in Catalan television about the case study of the participatory action in Barcelona
- P23 HERISCAPE- Heriscape, Italy
 - Information on an OIKONET-inspired workshop in Rimini was published in the

local web-journal RiminiSocial 2.0 with the title “All Inclusive – Workshop di Mediazione Sociale”.

- A brochure (in Italian) summarizing the activities of the participatory action in Rimini
- Conference “Housing sociale e partecipazione di comunità”, Rimini
- P23 BRATISLAVA, Slovakia
 - Radio report about one of the participatory actions organised by Bratislava municipality around the lake Zerník
- P25 ISCTE-IUL University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal
 - Article in the online version of the journal Homeland - News from Portugal
 - Presentation of the work of OIKONET on pedagogical innovation the “Seminário de Inovação Pedagógica no Ensino Superior e-Learning e Tecnologias Digitais”, ISCTE-IUL
- P26 AF BELGRADE- Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
 - Presentation “Strategic Thinking on Habitat Regeneration in Europe – the Serbian Participation in an Ongoing OIKONET Pedagogic Activity”, Tenth International Miklós Iványi PhD & DLA Symposium, University of Pécs; October 20–21, 2014
 - TV report Serbian National TV about the Belgrade workshop
 - Presentation of results of Belgrade workshop in the European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad
- P29 DIT- School of Architecture, Dublin Institute of Technology, Ireland
 - Chapter in the book “Renting in Ireland”, 2014
- P32 FAU- Facultad de Arquitectura y Urbanismo, Universidad de Chile
 - Announcement in the FAU website about Barcelona conference
- P34 HSUB- UN Habitat, Kenya
 - Publication of news in UN Habitat channels about their participation in OIKONET

Other partners took advantage of their participation in different events to disseminate project activities. Most of the partners posted information about the OIKONET project in the websites of their organizations.

1.3 Relations to other activities in the project

Some of the local dissemination activities reported in this document are complemented with videos which are available in the OIKONET YouTube channel (see Deliverable 7.2 Social Web). Information about the dissemination related to specific events carried out within WP3 Community Participation and WP4 Pedagogical Activities is included in the corresponding deliverables (see D3.3 “Report on participatory actions”, D4.1 “Learning Spaces” and D4.3 “International Workshops”).

2 PRINTED AND WEB MEDIA

A summary of the publications related to OIKONET project activities which appeared in local magazines and newspapers is presented in this section.

2.1 Contemporary living patterns – Homeland journal

An article in the online version of the journal Homeland - News from Portugal, reporting on the work done in the Lisbon workshop.

Paio, A., (2014) Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe

Link: <http://homeland.pt/contemporary-living-patterns-in-mass-housing-in-europe/>

Partner: ISCTE

Figure 1. Screenshot of the the article page on the web and the printed version if Homeland

The same article appeared in the printed version of the journal:

Paio, A. (2015) Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe. In Campos Costa, P. & Allegri, A. (eds.), Homeland News from Portugal (p. 522). Lisbon.

2.2 RiminiSocial 2.0 web-journal – information on a workshop

Information related to the participatory action carried out in Rimini appeared in the local web-journal RiminiSocial 2.0 under the title “All Inclusive – Workshop di Mediazione Sociale”.

Link: <http://www.newsrimini.it/2015/02/inclusive-workshop-di-mediazione-sociale>

Partner: HERISCAPE.

The screenshot shows a web page with a dark background and a collage of images. The main headline is "ALL INCLUSIVE - WORKSHOP DI MEDIAZIONE SOCIALE". Below it, there is a sub-headline "APPUNTAMENTI RIMINI" and a date "17 febbraio 2015, 17:33". The page is divided into several sections:

- ALTRI ARTICOLI RS2.0**: A list of other articles with titles like "Beni confiscati. Il dossier sulla Provincia: le ipoteche bloccano il riutilizzo a scopo sociale", "Premiazione del concorso per le scuole ispirato alla mostra Infanzia rubata", "Diritti in viaggio: a Rimini contro il razzismo", "Bando servizio civile. In provincia disponibili 193 posti", "35° Campo Lavoro Missionario, la presentazione (video)", "Parchi inclusivi: qualcosa si muove?", "Due bandi per contributi famiglie numerose e Tari", "Verità è giustizia", "Sportello sociale. 41 famiglie aiutate a pagare le rette della scuola", and "Padri al di là delle sbarre. Momenti di incontro e confronto con i figli per i papà detenuti".
- Main Article Text**:

Venerdì 20 febbraio 2015, dalle ore 10 alle ore 13 presso la Sala del Podestà, Piazza Cavour, Rimini, si svolgerà “**ALL INCLUSIVE**” workshop in occasione della prima Giornata Regionale della Mediazione Sociale, un'occasione per approfondire le potenzialità e le opportunità offerte dalla **Mediazione Sociale e dall'Housing Sociale**.

Durante il workshop, a cura della Cooperativa Sociale Fratelli è Possibile e D.N.A. – Rete dei Centri di Mediazione Sociale dell'Emilia Romagna, saranno previste incursioni teatrali a cura di NODI – Playback Factory, che con improvvisazioni teatrali attualizzeranno temi, emozioni, accadimenti, valori, sentimenti.

Nel pomeriggio RADIO ON THE ROAD – MEDIAZIONE 2.0: 2 ore di diretta radio (h. 16.00 – 18.00) presso l'Osteria Il Mare in piazza, via Luigi Poletti, 8 – Rimini centro

Live music, incontri, immagini, suoni, sapori. Bar aperto con.. Caffè sospeso!
- Info**: Cooperativa Sociale Fratelli è Possibile
tel. 0541 943647
e-mail cooperativa@ofscesen.it
- NOTIZIE CORRELATE**:
 - Agricoltura Sociale: convegno a Rimini** (19 febbraio 2014, 12:14)
 - La Formica Coop Soc al suo terzo bilancio sociale** (18 giugno 2014, 12:27)
- Redazione RiminiSocial 2.0**: A small graphic with logos and contact information.

Contatta la Redazione di Newsrimini tramite redazione@newsrimini.it o su Twitter [@newsrimini](https://twitter.com/newsrimini)

Figure 2. Screenshot of publication in on-line journal

2.3 FAU Noticias (Chile) - about Barcelona conference

Information about the first international conference in Barcelona was posted under the title “Académica de la FAU participará en conferencia de Red OIKONET” in the online news at the Faculty of Architecture and Urbanism of the University of Chile.

Link: <http://www.fau.uchile.cl/noticias/105131/academica-de-la-fau-participara-en-conferencia-de-red-oikonet>.

Partner: FAU

Portada U. de Chile Contacto Webmail Índice alfabético Acceso rápido a unidades. Buscar

FACULTAD DE ARQUITECTURA Y URBANISMO UNIVERSIDAD DE CHILE

académicos estudiantes egresados Geografía postulant Designo funcionarios

PORTADA FACULTAD DEPARTAMENTOS PREGRADO POSTGRADO INVESTIGACIÓN PUBLICACIONES EXTENSIÓN ADMISIÓN

Facultad de Arquitectura y Urbanismo

MÁS NOTICIAS

Investigador francés expuso en la FAU sobre conflicto y territorio

Coordinadora SIPEE FAU: "Esperamos seguir fortaleciendo el programa"

FAU prepara nutrida participación en la XIX Bienal de Arquitectura

Cuatro proyectos FAU fueron premiados en el CNPP 2015

Destacada participación de la FAU en ExpoMimbre Chimbarongo 2015

Documentales sobre conflictos urbanos se exhibirán en la FAU

Deporte FAU sigue creciendo el 2015

Declaración Pública sobre el edificio ubicado en Vicuña Mackenna 20

Protean 3 fue presentado en la Facultad de Medicina de la U. de Chile

Gladys "Laly" Elgueta, una vida en la FAU

Académica de la FAU participará en conferencia de Red OIKONET

La académica del Departamento de Urbanismo de la FAU, **profesora Viviana Fernández Prajoux**, asistirá a la primera conferencia de la **Red OIKONET**, que se realizará los días 25 y 26 de Septiembre en la Escuela de Arquitectura de La Salle de Barcelona, España.

La profesora Fernández, que integra formalmente la red, tendrá una activa participación en esta conferencia, presentando dos ponencias: "Desafíos actuales de la Política Habitacional en Chile" y "Participación comunitaria en el espacio público: el caso de los municipios de Santiago, Providencia y Recoleta, del Área Metropolitana de Santiago".

La académica también integrará el panel de discusión de cierre, compartiendo la mesa con la profesora Claire Lévy-Vroelant de la Universidad de Paris 8, Saint Dennis; Ekin Tam, del Play the City Studio y María Zwanenburg del Instituto de Estudios de Urbanos y de Vivienda de Holanda.

OIKONET es una red global multidisciplinaria de enseñanza e investigación en vivienda creada por el Programa de la Unión Europea "Lifelong Learning Programme". El principal objetivo para los tres años del programa es crear un espacio de colaboración e intercambio entre las universidades participantes para estudiar la vivienda contemporánea desde una perspectiva multidisciplinaria a través de sus tres grupos de trabajo: Vivienda Contemporánea, Actividades pedagógicas en torno al diseño habitacional y participación comunitaria y hábitat.

La red es dirigida por el académico Leandro Madrazo, de la Universidad de Arquitectura de La Salle, Barcelona; y la integran 34 universidades, principalmente europeas, siendo nuestra Facultad la única representante de una universidad latinoamericana.

Para mayor información pueden visitar el sitio www.oikonet.org o contactar a la profesora Viviana Fernández Prajoux: vfermand@uchilefau.cl.

Martes 9 de septiembre de 2014

BUSCADOR DE NOTICIAS

Por título o palabra clave

Volver Portada Imprimir Subir Enviar

Compartir: <http://uchile.cl/t105131>

Figure 3. Screenshot of the news in the university website

2.4 Information about OIKONET in RSP journal

The Croatian scientific journal *Revija za socijalnu politiku* published information about the international conference in Barcelona:

Bezovan, Gojko. Koje su globalne dimenzije stanovanja (Which are global dimensions of housing). *Croatian Journal of Social Policy*, 21:391-393, 2014.

Link: <http://www.rsp.hr/ojs2/index.php/rsp/article/viewFile/1247/1280>

Partner: PFZ

Rev. soc. polit., god. 21, br. 3, str. 385-393, Zagreb 2014.

Informacije i izvori

kih gradova. Ponovno se inzistiralo na konceptu integriranog održivog urbanog razvoja i socijalnim inovacijama, kao izrazu samoorganizacije, koje mogu pomoći u prevladavanju socijalne polarizacije u postsocijalističkim gradovima. Izazov je u izgradnji samoodrživih temelja urbanog razvoja kojima su potka pučke (eng. *grass root*) organizacije civilnog društva. Važno je znati učiti iz vlastitog i iskustva drugih te jasno prepoznati dodanu vrijednost razvojnih projekata.

Budućnost se postsocijalističkih gradova ne čini izglednom i ovisit će o cijelom nizu čimbenika, kao što su gospodarski rast, nezaposlenost, migracije, nastavak deindustrijalizacije te izglede uvođenja novog koncepta urbane vladavine poduprte EU sredstvima. Aktualizirana je i činjenica uvođenja novog koncepta urbanog planiranja koji će obuhvaćati funkcionalne urbane regije, a u kojem će značajniju ulogu igrati relevantni dionici.

Važno je spomenuti kako su na konferenciji mlade kolege iz regije, s iskustvom studija i istraživanja u zapadnim zemljama, iskazale stav prema starijim kolegama iz regije za koje drže da su previše kritični te da ne vide ipak pozitivne pomake koji se događaju u tranzicijskim zemljama.

Gojko Bežovan
Studijski centar socijalnog rada
Pravni fakultet Sveučilišta u Zagrebu

doi: 10.3935/rsp.v21i3.1247

KOJE SU GLOBALNE DIMENZIJE STANOVANJA

Barcelona, 25.-26. rujna 2014.

Prva međunarodna konferencija *Global dwelling* u okviru OIKONET projekta (www.oikonet.org) organizirana je u Barceloni 25.-26. rujna 2014.

U izvjesnom smislu ovo je nastavak ranijeg projekta OIKODOMOS – Virtualnog kampusa za promociju studija stanovanja u suvremenoj Europi (www.oikodomos.org).

Cilj projekta OIKONET – Globalna multidisciplinarna mreža o stambenim istraživanjima i učenju je stvoriti platformu suradnje za studij suvremenog stanovanja iz multidisciplinarnih i globalne perspektive obuhvaćajući višestruke dimenzije koje određuju oblike stanovanja u današnjim društvima: arhitektonske, urbane, ekološke, ekonomske, kulturne i društvene.

OIKONET obuhvaća 3 područja aktivnosti:

1. istraživanja o stambenim studijama kroz multidisciplinarni i globalni pristup
2. participativne akcije za uključivanje zajednica u definiranje, rješavanje i evaluiranje stambenih problema
3. pedagoške aktivnosti okupljanja različitih dionika, različite discipline i stvaranja okruženja za učenje.

U ovom trogodišnjem, Erasmus projektu cjeloživotnog učenja, sudjeluju 34 europske i svjetske organizacije, uključujući sveučilišta, istraživačke organizacije, gradove, stručne i organizacije civilnog društva. Projektna su aktivnosti započele u listopadu 2013. godine i trajat će 3 godine. Katedra za socijalnu politiku Studijskog centra socijalnog rada (Pravni fakultet) hrvatski je partner u ovom projektu.

Figure 4. Cover page of the Croatian Journal of Social Policy and the first page of the article

2.5 Paper Strategic Thinking on Habitat Regeneration in Europe

A paper with the title “Strategic Thinking on Habitat Regeneration in Europe – the Serbian Participation in an Ongoing OIKONET Pedagogic Activity” was presented at the Tenth International Miklós Iványi PhD & DLA Symposium (Architectural, Engineering and Information Sciences; University of Pécs; October 20–21, 2014 Pécs, Hungary), by Mirjana Devetaković and Tatjana Mrđenović

Link:

[http://phdsymp2014.pmmik.pte.hu/data/2014/1014/985/Time Table and Technical Program.pdf](http://phdsymp2014.pmmik.pte.hu/data/2014/1014/985/Time%20Table%20and%20Technical%20Program.pdf)

The paper was published in the proceedings:

Devetakovic, Mirjana - Mrdjenovic, Tatjana. Strategic Thinking on Habitat Regeneration in Europe – the Serbian Participation in an Ongoing OIKONET Pedagogic Activity. Abstract Proceedings Book, p.30, 10th PhD & DLA Symposium, University of Pecs, Hungary, 2014.

Partner: AF BELGRADE

2.6 Three chapters in the book “Selección de Proyectos” 2013-14

Carla Sentieri wrote three chapters of the book which describe the work carried out in the OIKONET project.

Sentieri Omarrementería, Carla. A collaborative learning space in the fundamentals of housing design and representation. In: Selección proyectos 2013-14. Departamento de Proyectos arquitectónicos, Ed. DPA. Universitat Politècnica de València. Pub. Laimprenta CG, Valencia. ISBN: 978-84-943704-2-7; pp 90-95.

Link: <http://dparq.upv.es/departamento/anuarios/anuario-2013-14/ipr-2013-14>

Figure 5. Pages with the beginning of the chapter in online version of the book

Sentieri Omarrementería, Carla. Different collaborative exercises. In: Selección proyectos 2013-14. Departamento de Proyectos arquitectónicos, Ed. Departamento de proyectos Arquitectónicos. Universitat Politècnica de València. Pub. Laimprenta CG, Valencia. ISBN: 978-84-943704-2-7; pp 174-176.

Link: <http://dparq.upv.es/departamento/anuarios/anuario-2013-14/pr1-2013-14>

Figure 6. Pages with the beginning of the chapter in online version of the book

Sentieri Omarrementería, Carla. Introduction to the project: an online collaborative space through the basics of design and representation of housing. In: Selección proyectos 2013-14. Departamento de Proyectos arquitectónicos, Departamento de Proyectos Arquitectónicos. Universitat Politècnica de València. Pub. Laimprenta CG, Valencia. ISBN: 978-84-943704-2-7; pp 18-26.

Link: <http://dparq.upv.es/departamento/anuarios/anuario-2013-14/escritos-2013-14>

Partner: ETSA-UPV

Figure 7. Pages with the beginning of the chapter in online version of the book

2.7 Information on the UN-Habitat website about the 2nd OIKONET Conference

News about the participation of UN Habitat in the second international conference in Bratislava appeared in the organization website.

Link: <https://unhabitat.org/un-habitat-participates-in-oikonet-conference>

Partner: HSUB

Figure 8. UN-Habitat webpage with the information on the OIKONET converence in Bratislava

2.8 Article about the OIKONET Bratislava conference in RSP journal

An article about the second international conference in Bratislava appeared in the Croatian scientific journal Revija za socijalnu politiku.

Josip Pandžić: OIKONET Conference: Global Dwelling: Housing Regeneration Strategies. Revija za socijalnu politiku (Croatian Journal of Social Policy), Vol.22 No.3 pp. 415-419.

Link: <http://hrcak.srce.hr/file/220638>

Partner: PFZ

Rev. soc. polit., god. 22, br. 3, str. 403-422, Zagreb 2015.

Informacije i osvrni

Rev. soc. polit., god. 22, br. 3, str. 403-422, Zagreb 2015.

Informacije i osvrni

Na radionici »Tržišta privatnog najma« pod vodstvom Boba Jordana iz Irske, Carla Earharta iz SAD-a održala je izlaganje »Terminologija stambene industrije« u novinskim člancima na Internetu u kojem je izložila rezultate analize utjecaja medijskih strategija na percepciju javnosti o stanovanju i stambenim statusima predloživši aktivnije zagovaranje nove stambene terminologije koja bi imala snažni de-stigmatizacijski ulogu u javnom diskursu.

Jozsef Hegedus i Vera Horvath iz Mađarske održali su opsežno izlaganje »Elementi konvergenije i divergenije: modeli privatnog najamnog sektora u središnjoj i istočnoj Europi« u kojemu su predstavili rezultate komparativnog istraživanja trendova privatnog najamnog sektora u tranzicijskim zemljama posljednjih 25 godina i pritom ukazali na nedostatak i neusporednost podataka, a time i nemogućnost pouzdane procjene tog sektora. Visok udio stanova u privatnom vlasništvu te problemi proizašli iz (političkom voljom) ubrzanih procesa privatizacije, decentralizacije i denacionalizacije stanovanja stavljani su u kontekst analize djelovanja stambenih aktera sa strane ponude i potražnje. Segmentacija tržišta najamnog stanovanja podložnog tržišnim ciklusima i sveprisutna diskriminacija najamoprimalca zbog učestalosti neformalnih, a time i ilegalnih ugovora s najmodavcima čini ovaj sektor nepredvidivim za obje dogovorne strane te su stoga izlagači upozorili da bi se u vrijeme stambene krize problemi javnog najamnog sektora trebali više naslovljavati pri sačinjavanju javnih politika. Ovo je istraživanje dio projekta koji će rezultirati izdavanjem knjige na tu temu, gdje se očekuje da će biti poglavlje o Hrvatskoj.

Brojnost sudionika ove konferencije nije bila tek posljedica vještog iskoristavanja prilike za ljetni posjet portugalskoj metropoli, već odraz porasta zanimanja za problemne stambene i urbane politike po-

slijednih godina. Domaćini konferencije zaslužuju svaku pohvalu zbog zavidne razine organizacije skupa, radionica, izleta i neformalnih druženja čime su pridonijeli istraživačkim suradnjama i razmjenama stručnih iskustava u budućnosti.

Konferencija Europske mreže stambenih istraživača 2016. godine bit će organizirana u Belfastu.

Josip Pandžić
Poslijediplomski doktorski studij
socijalne politike

doi: 10.3935/rsp.v22i3.1345

OIKONET KONFERENCIJA: STRATEGIJE URBANE OBNOVE

Batistava, 25. rujna 2015.

Druga međunarodna konferencija *Global Dwelling: Housing Regeneration Strategies* u okviru OIKONET projekta (www.oikonet.org) organizirana je u Bratislavi 25. rujna 2015.

U radu konferencije sudjelovalo je pedesetak izlagača s ukupno 11 izlaganja, dok je otvaranje izložbe od 22 projekta postera rezervirano za zatvaranje konferencije.

Nakon uvodnih riječi dekanice Arhitektonskog fakulteta u Bratislavi, Lubice Vitkove i voditelja OIKONET projekta Leandra Madrazza, konferencija je otvorena plenarnim izlaganjem profesora *emeritusa* arhitekture i urbanog dizajna Richarda Haywarda iz Ujedinjenog Kraljevstva pod nazivom »Le Corbusierov« stroy u kojem se stanuje 'ili krtica kuća u 'Vjetru u vrbama' – omogućavajuće i onemogućavajuće arhitekture i urbanizma«. U svojem se izlaganju dotaknuo velikog broja tema među kojima se istaknula problematizacija načina usklađivanja često apstraktnih teorijskih znanja

o stanovanju i održivom urbanom razvoju (Habitat III) održat će se 2016. u Quitu.

Andrej Tokajuk iz Poljske održao je izlaganje pod nazivom »Standardi najamnih stanova sagrađenih od strane udruge za socijalno stanovanje u Białystoku nakon 1996.«. Tranzicijska iskustva Poljske u području stanovanja vrlo su slična iskustvima ostalih zemalja bivšeg realosocijalističkog bloka pa je u izlaganju predstavljena geneza prnšivost stanovanja od socijalističkog razdoblja do suvremenih oblika stambene opskrbe nakon 1989. – stambenih programa na nacionalnoj, regionalnoj te lokalnoj razini uz nezostavnu ulogu neprofitnih stambenih organizacija. Studija slučajja naselja s uspješno implementiranim programom socijalnog/prnšivost stanovanja u gradu Białystoku, izlagaču je poslužila kao empirijski primjer za potkrepju zagovaračkih aktivnosti dekomodificiranog stanovanja na nacionalnoj razini. Rezultati mjerenja kvalitete stanovanja u naselju, upotrebom parametrijske metode na nekoliko okolišnih i stambenih faktora, pokazali su da se radi o programu vrjednog re-implementacije u drugim urbanim kontekstima diljem Poljske.

Posljednje izlaganje na konferenciji održao je Ognjen Marina iz Makedonije, naziva »Od narativa do strategija: regeneracija kroz uvjete urbanih granica u Skoplju«. Postmodernistički *impetus* ovog izlaganja zasnovan je na raznim projektima urbane obnove u Skoplju, kojima je izlagač želio istražiti javne, privatne i kolektivne sfere grada »identifikacijom socio-prostornih dinamika postojećih urbanih konstrukcija, urbanih fragmenata i praznina, linija podjele i gradskih mrežava« kako bi se pokušalo objasniti kaotični razvoj spontanog grada po pitanju prostorne veličine i gustoće naseljenosti. Analizirajući urbane narative«

izlagač je pokušao ponuditi novu viziju održivih obrazaca urbanog razvoja koji, prema njegovim riječima, »može ovisiti o političkoj volji različitih makedonskih vladav.«

Konferencija je zatvorena kratkom plenarnom diskusijom koju je moderirao Karim Hadjri iz Velike Britanije, uz sudjelovanje plenarnih izlagača Richarda Haywarda i Aseema Inama. Posljednja međunarodna konferencija OIKONET projekta 2016. godine bit će organizirana u Prestonu.

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socijalne politike

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EUROPEAN SUMMER SCHOOL ON SOCIAL ECONOMY »PERSONALISATION AND SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP«

Bertinoro, 6. - 11. srpnja 2015.

Europska ljetna škola o socijalnoj ekonomiji (ESSE) *Personalisation and Social Entrepreneurship* održala se od 6. do 11. srpnja 2015. u Sveučilišnom rezidencij-skom centru, Bertinoro Italija.

Ljetnu školu organizirali su Sveučilište u Bologni i udruga AICCON. Sveučilište u Bologni smatra se najstarijim sveučilištem u zapadnom svijetu. Unutar njegovih sastavnica, u zadnje vrijeme postoje značajni istraživački naponi u područjima transformacije socijalne države kao i razvoja socijalnog poduzetništva i socijalnih inovacija. AICCON¹ je talijanska udruga osnovana

¹ Dodatne informacije o ljetnoj školi možete pronaći na: <http://www.esse.unibo.it/>.

² Više informacija o udruzi na: <http://www.aiccon.it/index.cfm>.

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Figure 9. Journal cover page; first and the last page of the article

2.9 Announcements of the “Thinking Dwelling” program

Information about the first and second editions of the “Thinking Dwelling” collaborative learning programme was posted in the blog of the School of Architecture La Salle.

Links: <http://blogs.salleurl.edu/arquitectura/thinking-dwelling/>

<http://blogs.salleurl.edu/arquitectura/la-salle-acoge-programa-thinking-dwelling/>

Partner: LA SALLE

Figure 10. Announcement of the first edition “Thinking Dwelling” program on the blog of La Salle

2.10 Publication of the outcomes of the “Thinking Dwelling” program

The contributions of the participants in the first edition of the “Thinking Dwelling” program were compiled in a publication by the School of Architecture La Salle. Copies of the printed publication were handed out to the partners, and an on-line version is available at the project website.

Link: http://issuu.com/oikonet/docs/revista_final

Partner: LA SALLE

Figure 11. Inside pages with works submitted by participants

2.11 Chapter in the book “Renting in Ireland”

In the book “Renting in Ireland”, a chapter entitled “Fit for renting: an investigation into space standards of Irish housing” was co-written by Noel Brady and Jim Roche. The work reported in the publication deals with space standards in Irish rental housing and it is based on the project outcomes.

Noel Brady and Jim Roche: Fit for renting: An investigation into space standards of Irish

housing. In: Lorcan Sirr (ed.): *Renting in Ireland*. Dublin: Institute of Public Administration, 2014, pp.222-240.

Link: <http://arrow.dit.ie/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1001&context=beschrebk> ^

Partner: DIT

Figure 12. Cover and the contents of the book “Renting in Ireland”

2.12 Leaflet participatory action in Rimini

A brochure (in Italian) summarizing the activities of the participatory action in Rimini (see Deliverable 3.3 “Report on participatory actions”) was produced and distributed among the participants from Rimini. It is also available on line in the project website.

Link: <https://issuu.com/oikonet/docs/20160404-rimini-leaflet>

Partners: HERISCAPE, OAPPCR

Figure 13. Brochure to disseminate the results of the community action in Rimini

3 EVENTS

3.1 Conference “Housing sociale e partecipazione di comunità”, Rimini

The Chamber of Architects of Rimini and Heriscape organized a one-day conference in Rimini, September 27, 2016, on the theme “Housing sociale e partecipazione di comunità” With this opportunity, the outcomes of the participatory action implemented by the two OIKONET partners in Rimini were discussed. The meeting was recorded and it is available in YouTube.

Links: <http://www.architettirimini.net/arc/eventi-2016/31-eventi/1136-27-09-16-housing-sociale-e-partecipazione-di-comunita>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sRdZqxaILUI&feature=youtu.be&t=2m30s>

Partners: HERISCAPE, OAPPCR

The screenshot shows the website of the Chamber of Architects of Rimini. The header includes the logo and name: "ordine degli architetti, pianificatori, paesaggisti e conservatori della provincia di rimini". The navigation menu includes: HOME, ORDINE, NEWSLETTERS, AGENDA, CONSIGLIO DISCIPLINA, STRUMENTI, EVENTI, INFORMATIVA LOCALE, L'ASSOCIAZIONE.

The main content area is titled "EVENTI" and shows a list of events for the years 2017, 2016, 2015, 2014, 2013, and 2012. The event for 2016 is highlighted: "CONVEGNO 'HOUSING SOCIALE E PARTECIPAZIONE DI COMUNITÀ'". Below the title, there is a link to the video of the event: "LINK AL VIDEO DELL'EVENTO".

The announcement text states: "Allegato alla presente si trasmette locandina del Convegno dal titolo 'Housing sociale e partecipazione di comunità' organizzato dall'Ordine in collaborazione con HERISCAPE e Oikonet - 27 settembre 2016 presso Palazzo Agolanti. CFP concessi n. 4".

Below the text, there is a button for "ISCRIZIONE eventi formativi" and a large image of the event flyer. The flyer features the text: "Convegno Housing sociale e partecipazione di comunità", "27 | SETTEMBRE | 2016 | ORE 9,15 - 13,15", "PALAZZO AGOLANTI - VIA GAMBALLINGA, 29 - RIMINI", "PROMOSSO DALL'ORDINE DEGLI ARCHITETTI PPC, DI RIMINI - IN COLLABORAZIONE CON ARCHIRI, HERISCAPE E OIKONET".

At the bottom of the flyer, it says: "L'Ordine degli architetti di Rimini, assieme all'associazione Heriscape, ha partecipato alla ricerca Europea Oikonet (http://www.oikonet.org) che si è posta l'obiettivo di costituire uno spazio internazionale di collaborazione per lo studio e la ricerca sull'housing contemporaneo." and "ORE 09,15 | REGISTRAZIONE PARTECIPANTI".

Figure 14. Conference announcement in the website of the Chamber of Architects

Figure 16. Presentation of the Lisbon Workshop - seminar “Pedagogical Innovation in Higher Education”

3.3 OIKONET presentation at the LESEC Annual Event 2016

Tomas Ooms gave a presentation titled “An OIKONET Design Studio Showcase: Blended learning in a global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning” during the [Annual Event 2016 “Blended learning”](http://set.kuleuven.be/LESEC/news-events/annual-event-2016/Ooms) of the Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center (LESEC) at the KU Leuven.

Link: <http://set.kuleuven.be/LESEC/news-events/annual-event-2016/Ooms>

Partner: KUL

Figure 17. Event webpage and one of the presentation slides

3.4 Presentations at the “Jornades d’Innovació Docent”, Ramon Lull University

In June 2016, two one-day conferences dedicated to presenting and discussing projects on pedagogical innovation were organized at the School of Architecture Engineering La Salle (June 15) and at the Ramon Llull University (June 29). The work carried out in OIKONET was presented by Leandro Madrazo, Angel Martin Cojo and Adrià Sanchez Llorens. Two posters were presented in a poster session.

Partner: LA SALLE

Figure 18. OIKONET poster presented at La Salle and Ramon Llull University conferences on pedagogical innovation

Figure 19. "Thinking Dwelling" poster presented at La Salle and Ramon Llull University conferences on pedagogical innovation

3.5 Presentations in the European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad

Posters with the work done by students at the Belgrade workshop were displayed at the European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad, June 11, 2016. Students presented the works to a representative of the developer of the Belgrade Waterfront project.

Partner: AF BELGRADE

Figure 20. Announcement of the OIKONET Belgrade Workshop promotion in the European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad

Figure 21. Project introduction and students' presentations at the European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad, Belgrade

3.6 Other events

A round table on the theme “How to strengthen social cohesion in Novi Jelkovec settlement?” took place at the University of Zagreb on November 20, 2013 (Gojko Bezovan, Ognjrn Caldaroovic, Tihomir Jukic). The OIKONET project was introduced during this round table.

On the symposium “University Transformation from the Community Perspective”, held at the University of Puerto Rico, 7 to 11 April 2015, Omayra Rivera presented the OIKONET project.

The Grenfell-Baines School of Architecture, Construction and Environment of University of Central Lancashire (UCLAN), held its annual school postgraduate student research event on Wednesday the June 18, 2014. This event provides postgraduate research students at all stages

of their study with the opportunity to showcase their research project, and present some of its key findings in form of a poster presentation. On this occasion Professor Karim Hadjri and Isaiah Oluremi Durosaiye prepared a poster about the OIKONET Project. The contribution of UCLAN, as the leader of the research work package, was presented on this poster. The poster presentation was received with exceptional interest from students and members of staff alike. Colleagues across various disciplines were impressed by the kind of impact the Grenfell-Baines School of Architecture, Construction and Environment makes on research.

4 RADIO AND TELEVISION

Some of the OIKONET activities have also been presented on radio and television programs.

4.1 MONOCLE on-line radio: OIKONET research network

A one-hour long “Lisbon Housing Special” was broadcast on July 29, 2014 on Monocle. The program reports on two contrasting areas of the city, Bairro da Liberdade and Portela de Sacavem, to examine the legacy of Lisbon’s housing programs over the past five decades. Additionally, it reports on housing initiatives pursued by Lisbon City Hall and looks at the work of the OIKONET research network.

Link: <http://monocle.com/radio/shows/section-d/146/>

Figure 22. Screenshot of archived broadcast page

4.2 Participatory action in the Catalan Public Television TV3

A TV-shot (5:44 min.) was broadcast at Catalan Public Television in November 2014. It includes the case of study provided by Sostre Cívic for the participatory action in Barcelona was show in this report.

Link: https://www.dropbox.com/s/ydb1riyjeo5ljjx/VTS_01_1.VOB?dl=0

Partner: SOSTRE CIVIC

Figure 23. Screenshots of the recorded TV-shot

4.3 Slovak Radio informs about participatory action in Bratislava

A report on one of the participatory actions organised by Bratislava municipality about the future development of the area around the lake Zemník, was broadcast May 19, 2016 on the Radio Regina – the regional broadcast station of the Slovak Radio.

Link: <https://reginazapad.rtvs.sk/clanky/z-regionov/107255/jazero-zemnik>

Partner: BRATISLAVA

Figure 24. Archived page of the broadcast about the participative event in Bratislava

4.4 Debate in Radio Ciutat Vella, Barcelona: Liveable cities

On February 1, 2017, Leandro Madrazo, Ángel Martin Cojo and Cynthia Echave participated in a debate in the local Radio Ciutat Vella, in Barcelona. They were invited to talk about the work done by students in the “Urban Systems” OIKONET elective course which was dedicated to analysing four urban axes in the city -Rambla Guipúscoa, Rambla del Poble Nou, Rambla del Raval and Avinguda Mistral- and to making proposals to make these spaces more liveable with the collaboration of neighbours.

Figure 25. A moment of the interview in Radio Ciutat Vella, Barcelona

4.5 TV report on the Serbian National Broadcasting Service

A 4-minute report on the work done in the Belgrade workshop was produced by the Serbian National TV and screened in the TV Show “Žikina šarenica“, broadcast both in Serbia and globally via RTS satellite programme.

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rnKQQlnVMIY>

Partner: AF BELGRADE

Figure 26. Images from the TV report

5 WEBSITES

The following partners have disseminated the OIKONET project in their websites.

LA SALLE	http://blogs.salleurl.edu/lasalleuniversities/2013/09/09/oikonet-starts-a-course-on-contemporary-housing/
ETSA-UPV	http://dparq.upv.es/eventos *
FASTU	http://www.fa.stuba.sk/sk/dianie-na-fakulte/aktuality/oikonet.html?page_id=3377
KUL	https://arch.kuleuven.be/english/news/oikonet-expanding-the-oikodomos-virtual-campus-experience
USI	http://search.usi.ch/projects/723/OIKONET
CHALMERS	http://www.chalmers.se/en/departments/arch/industry-society/Pages/OIKONET.aspx
PFZ	http://www.ihs.nl/research/research_projects/oikonet/
UKIM	http://www.arh.ukim.edu.mk/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=1&Itemid=4 *
OAPPCR	http://www.architettirimini.net/arc/images/newsletters/2014/News%20n.%2001-2014.pdf *
UL	http://www.ee.fs.uni-lj.si/LOTZ/projekti.html
AAU	http://www.create.aau.dk/index.php/architecture/news/826-department-takes-part-in-the-oikonet-research-project *
RTU	http://www.rtu.lv/content/view/10751/2303/lang,lv/ http://www.rtu.lv/en/content/view/3971/2078/lang,en/ *
UCY	http://webapps.leventis.ucy.ac.cy:7786/public/weblinks/download_pck.download?p_file=F1928845728/OIKOnet.pdf * http://ucy.ac.cy/arch/en/
UCLAN	http://www.uclan.ac.uk/news/modern_housing_issues_addressed_through_global_research.php
PFZ	http://www.pravo.unizg.hr/scsr/ksp?@=6nmg#news_15596
UGA	http://www.urbanisme-grenoble.com/1-international/les-projets-internationaux/42-oikonet *
NOVA	http://www.hioa.no/eng/Om-HiOA/Senter-for-velferds-og-arbeidslivsforskning/NOVA/NOVA-prosjekter/Aldring-og-bolig/Oikonet
HERISCAPE	http://www.heriscape.eu/OIKOnet_poster_announcement_20130909.pdf *
BRATISLAVA	http://www.bratislava.sk/vismo/dokumenty2.asp?id_org=700000&p1=11049956&id=11042946
ISCTE	http://www.iscte-iul.pt/home/noticias.aspx?NewsID=6c555410-ec3f-4a10-bab2-5d987c9906d9
AF_BELGRADE	http://www.bg.ac.rs/en/international/projects/llp-projects.php
BUT	http://wa.pb.edu.pl/aktualnosci/OIKONET,965.html
ELTE	http://www.tatk.elte.hu/kiemelt-projektjeink/oikonet-projekt *
DIT	http://www.dit.ie/news/archive2014/dit-collaborates-on-eu-funded-global-housing-research-programme/
HSUB	www.gnshousing.org

6 CONCLUSIONS

The main goal of the dissemination through local media was to reach the local stakeholders involved in the workshops and participatory actions. This goal has been mostly achieved: the work done in two of the three international workshops has been broadcast on radio (Lisbon) and television (Belgrade); three of the four participatory actions have been disseminated on radio (Bratislava), television (Barcelona) and through leaflets (Rimini).

In addition, the project outcomes have been published in yearbooks published by the School of Architecture of Valencia and Dublin Institute of Technology, and a compendium of the results of the learning programme “Thinking Dwelling” was produced by the School of Architecture La Salle.

Three partners have presented the work done in the OIKONET project in forums dedicated to discussions on pedagogical innovation at their institutions: ISCTE, KUL and LA SALLE.

Most partners (25 out of 34) have posted information about the existence of the OIKONET project in their websites. Furthermore, a few of them have continued to post news about the participation in the project activities in partners’ websites.